

A predictive model for postpartum depression: ensemble learning strategies in machine learning

Winda Ayu Fazraningtyas^{1,2}, Bahbibi Rahmatullah¹, Husni Naparin³, Mohammad Basit⁴,
Nor Asiah Razak¹

¹Faculty of Computing and Meta-Technology, Sultan Idris Education University, Perak, Malaysia

²Department of Maternity Nursing, Faculty of Health, Sari Mulia University, Banjarmasin, Indonesia

³Department of Information Technology, Faculty of Science and Technology, Sari Mulia University, Banjarmasin, Indonesia

⁴Department of Management in Nursing, Faculty of Health, Sari Mulia University, Banjarmasin, Indonesia

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ABSTRACT

Postpartum depression (PPD) presents a significant mental health challenge for mothers following childbirth. While the precise cause of this condition remains unknown, preventive measures and treatments are available. This study aims to employ ensemble learning techniques, utilizing C4.5 decision tree (DT), gradient boosting tree (GBT), and extreme gradient boosting (XGBoost), to predict the occurrences of PPD in the Banjarmasin, South Kalimantan, Indonesia. The predictive model developed encompasses a dataset comprising 317 records gathered from postpartum mothers in hospitals, community health services, and midwifery clinics (referred to as Model 1). Furthermore, resampling techniques (Model 2) were employed to address class imbalance. Additionally, feature selection including forward selection and backward elimination (Model 3) were implemented to enhance model performance. The findings reveal that XGBoost, combined with resampling methods, achieved the highest accuracy rate at 87.57%. Feature selection identified five crucial factors associated with PPD incidence: marital status, number of living children, history of depression, fear of delivery, and family relationships. The utilization of ensemble learning strategies for PPD prediction yields reliable outcomes that can be applied within clinical settings. Exploring alternative ensemble learning strategies such as random forest and adaptive boosting could further optimize model performance and warrant consideration in future research endeavours.

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Corresponding Author:

Bahbibi Rahmatullah

Faculty of Computing and Meta-Technology, Sultan Idris Education University

Perak, Malaysia

Email: bahbibi@meta.upsi.edu.my

1. INTRODUCTION

Reproductive health frequently overlooks mental health considerations [1] despite ongoing surveillance revealing a significant prevalence of mental health issues. This multifaceted health condition encompasses a range from optimal well-being to the initiation of emotional distress and pain. Mental health disorders can inflict prolonged suffering on individuals [2], occurring across various environments and affecting anyone, even mothers, during childbirth. The postpartum phase emerges as the most precarious time for both the mother and the baby, often overlooked and associated with a significant number of fatalities [3]. It marks a crucial period of maternal transformation characterized by physiological and psychological changes. Postpartum depression (PPD) stands out as a severe mental health issue [4], one that can be

addressed and treated yet frequently goes unnoticed and undiagnosed [5]. PPD is intricately linked to a combination of physical and emotional factors.

Machine learning (ML) has become an interesting topic in research related to early detection [6], [7]. Early detection of depressive symptoms can significantly improve depression management and reduce its negative impacts [8]. However, routine screening for PPD is often neglected due to the non-economical nature of traditional and time-consuming self-report questionnaires. Based on a systematic literature review and meta-analysis, the prevalence of PPD was found to be 17.22% in the world population, while the rate of PPD was much lower in developed or high-income countries and regions [9]. Meanwhile, in Indonesia, the prevalence of perinatal mental health incidents is not yet known [10]. Research by Fazraningtyas [11] on 88 participants who were hospitalized at the General Hospital in the Banjarmasin area revealed that 17% of postpartum mothers experienced severe depression. This figure is concerning, considering there is no reliable prediction tool for detecting PPD incidents, which impacts the handling of this case.

Studies on predicting PPD cases remain limited and have not yielded significant results. A systematic literature review approach shows that optimizing the performance of ML algorithms varies depending on the dataset and the problem to be addressed [12], [13]. In addition, a systematic literature review study revealed that the random forest (RF) algorithm consistently provided the best prediction model performance [12], with an accuracy of 79.1% in a retrospective cohort study [14]. The extreme randomized forest (XRT) [15] and logistic regression (LR) [16] models achieved a 73% accuracy in PPD prediction. Despite these efforts, the effectiveness of PPD prediction models remains suboptimal, suggesting a need for further research. Ensemble learning, as noted by Raza *et al.* [17], has shown improved performance and potential for predicting PPD.

This study investigates the use of artificial intelligent (AI), particularly ML and ensemble learning, to predict PPD occurrence and evaluate key contributing factors. It optimizes the chosen learning algorithm with various sampling methods and employs forward selection and backward elimination for feature selection. An ensemble learning model, including C4.5 decision tree (DT), gradient boosting tree (GBT), and extreme gradient boosting (XGBoost), is applied to improve model performance by providing stability to the prediction model. The goal is to enhance healthcare development and provide actionable insights for clinical settings using AI.

2. METHOD

The framework illustrated in Figure 1 delineates the consecutive phases and sequential steps employed in this research. The gathered data undergoes processing to prepare it for utilization in ML algorithms. The ML algorithms utilized in this study encompass C4.5 DT, GBT, and XGBoost. The constructed predictive model incorporates data processing, segregation, feature selection, and prediction algorithms [18]. These models are configured to optimize the performance of ML algorithms effectively utilizing resampling and feature selection methodologies.

Figure 1. The framework of the study

2.1. Data collection

The dataset for this study was collected from 317 postpartum mothers at hospitals, community health services, and midwifery clinics in Banjarmasin city, using purposive sampling. The edinburgh

postnatal depression scale (EPDS) and the postpartum depression risk factors (PPDRF) were utilized as measurement instruments. This questionnaire is available in Indonesian, with construct validation using confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) to obtain a factor loading score of more than 0.5, a comparative fit index (CFI) value of 0.963, and a normed fit index (NFI) of 0.942 [19]. The EPDS is a 10-item questionnaire that is easy to administer and is an effective screening tool. Each question is scored from 0 to 3. For questions 1, 2, and 4, the scoring is from 0 to 3, while for questions 3, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, and 10, the scoring is from 3 to 0. The maximum score on this questionnaire is 30. According to Levis *et al.* [20], a threshold value of 11 or higher may indicate women who are at risk of PPD.

2.2. Data preprocessing: resampling methods

The resampling technique addresses imbalanced learning data by modifying it to achieve a balanced distribution [21]. This research employed random oversampling, including bootstrapping and SMOTE methods. Bootstrapping involves selecting n observations from an original dataset of size n with replacement, allowing some observations to be duplicated and others omitted. The process is mathematically detailed in the provided:

$$X_i^* = \text{Randomly choose } X_j \text{ from } \{X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n\} \quad (1)$$

where X_i^* represents each element in the bootstrap sample that is replicated from the original dataset.

SMOTE is a data preprocessing approach to tackle class imbalance within a dataset. This technique involves generating new synthetic observations derived from the existing samples of the minority class. Generating these synthetic training records involves randomly selecting one or more K -nearest neighbours for each instance in the minority class. The (2) elucidates the formulation of this method for creating synthetic samples:

$$X_i^* = X_i + \lambda \cdot (X_{nnj} - X_i) \quad (2)$$

The factor λ , ranging between 0 and 1, plays a pivotal role in determining the distance between X_i and X_{nnj} for the creation of synthetic samples. In this study, the number of neighbours was 5.

2.3. Feature selection

Feature selection is a technique to diminish input variables in a prediction model. It achieves this by maximizing the inclusion of pertinent data while eliminating noise from the dataset. This automatic process optimizes relevant features to enhance model performance [21]. Forward selection (FS) is an iterative process that commences by identifying the feature with the highest performance concerning the target feature. In selecting feature subsets, stratification is imperative to ensure adequate representation of each class [22]. Backward elimination (BE) is a valuable tool for selecting pertinent features prior to entering the model testing phase. This algorithm initiates by testing all features and progressively eliminates non-significant features by comparing the results derived from each combination of these features [23], [24].

2.4. Cross validation

Cross-validation (CV) is a model training approach that evaluates prediction accuracy. This technique is particularly advantageous for estimating low-bias models, making it widely adopted in ML algorithms [25]. The present research employs a k -fold CV strategy, dividing the dataset into k subsets. Initially, the sample is randomly partitioned into k subsamples of equal size. Each of the k subsamples functions as validation data exactly once after the cross-validation technique is iteratively applied k times [26]. For this study, a 10-fold CV was implemented with stratified sampling.

2.5. Machine learning algorithms

The fundamental concept behind ensemble learning involves training multiple weak classifiers with training data and then combining these weak classifiers to construct a robust classifier [27], [28]. Ensemble models represent a potent ML approach that has demonstrated tangible advantages in various applications [29], [30]. Generally, the generalization ability of ensembles surpasses that of essential learners [30]. This model was developed using C4.5 DT, GBT, and XGBoost learning algorithms.

2.5.1. C4.5 decision tree

DT constitutes a sequential model that efficiently and cohesively combines a series of basic tests, wherein numerical features are compared with threshold values in each test [31]. DT analysis serves as a technique for categorizing target factor categories by formulating decision-making rules in the structure of a

tree [32]. This study employed the C4.5 algorithm, which represents an advancement over the ID3 algorithm. The C4.5 algorithm addresses the limitations inherent in the ID3 algorithm [33].

$$\begin{aligned} H(T) &= -\sum_{i=1}^c p_i \cdot \log_2(p_i) \\ \text{Gain}(T, A) &= H(T) - \sum_{v \in \text{Value}(A)} \frac{|T_v|}{|T|} \cdot H(T_v) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

T denotes the training example, c represents the number of classes, p_i is the proportion of examples in class i , A signifies the feature, $\text{Value}(A)$ encompass the potential values of attribute A , T_v denotes the subset of T for which attribute A has the value v , dan $|T|$ indicates the size of the set.

2.5.2. Gradient boosted tree

The GBT algorithm combines regression and classification tree models similar to DT to improve predictive accuracy by iteratively refining estimates. It uses a nonlinear regression approach to increase tree precision and addresses prediction model issues [34] through an iterative boosting process, described by the formula provided.

$$F_m(x) = F_{m-1}(x) + \rho \cdot h_m(x) \quad (4)$$

In this formula, $F_m(x)$ represents the predictive function after including the m^{th} tree, $F_{m-1}(x)$ represents the predictive function after including the $(m-1)^{\text{th}}$ tree, ρ is the learning rate, which is a hyperparameter that determines the influence of each tree, and h_m denotes the m^{th} weak learner that is trained on the negative gradient of the loss function.

2.5.3. Extreme gradient boosting

XGBoost represents a fusion of bagging and boosting algorithms, commencing with constructing a weaker learner model and progressively enhancing its accuracy sequentially [35]. The initial tree in XGBoost tends to be weaker in classification, employing probability initialization. Subsequent weight updates are applied to each constructed tree, resulting in an ensemble of classification trees. The formula employed in this algorithm is as:

$$\hat{y}_i = \sum_{t=1}^T f_t(x_i), f_t \in F \quad (5)$$

In the given context, $f_t(x_i)$ symbolizes the predicted value of the t^{th} residual tree for the t^{th} residual, where $x_i - y_i$ denotes the predicted value of the model. The term f_i corresponds to the residual number in the t^{th} round. Additionally, F represents the residual tree function's vacant space [36].

2.6. Evaluation metrics

Evaluation involves assessing the performance of the constructed prediction model. In this research, the evaluation process depicted in the Table 1 involved examining achievements in accuracy, recall, precision, and specificity.

Table 1. Evaluation metrics of the study

Performance metrics	Equation	Number of equations
Accuracy	$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{tp + tn}{tp + fp + tn + fn}$	(6)
Recall	$\text{Precision} = \frac{tp}{tp + fp}$	(7)
Precision	$\text{Sensitivity} = \frac{tp}{tp + fn}$	(8)
Specificity	$\text{Specificity} = \frac{tn}{tn + fp}$	(9)

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study compares the effectiveness of three ensemble algorithms C4.5, GBT, and XGBoost for predicting PPD in postpartum mothers. This research involved 317 participants and 32 variables, including 31 independent variables and one dependent variable. The study found that 27.13% of postpartum mothers were at risk of developing PPD (minority class), while 72.87% were not at risk (majority class). This dataset was used as input for the predictive model in Table 2.

Table 2 delineates the experiments conducted, which are employed in three prediction models, each with its unique characteristics. Model 1 centres on the original dataset results, integrated into ensemble

learning. Conversely, Model 2 concentrates on refining the model through data preprocessing, employing resampling techniques such as Bootstrapping and SMOTE. Meanwhile, Model 3 incorporates feature selection, specifically FS and BE, yielding feature importance. The outcomes of implementing this structured model are presented in Table 3.

Table 2. Design processes of the PPD model prediction

Type of models	Architecture of the model
Model 1	Dataset + CV + ML algorithms + evaluation metrics
Model 2	Dataset + resampling methods (Bootstrapping and SMOTE) + CV + ML algorithms + evaluation metrics
Model 3	Dataset + feature selection (forward selection and backward elimination) + CV + ML algorithms + evaluation metrics

Table 3. Evaluation of PPD model prediction

Algorithms	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	Specificity
Model 1				
C4.5 DT	68.77	42.02	16.25	88.32
GBT	63.77	38.83	48.19	69.75
XGBoost	67.83	39.39	21.94	84.86
Model 2				
C4.5 DT	69.51	72.10	66.32	72.55
GBT	69.95	68.36	76.71	63.06
XGBoost	87.57	87.46	88.42	86.79
Model 3				
C4.5 DT + FS	78.27	82	28.33	96.96
GBT + FS	72.88	-	0	100
XGBoost + FS	77.94	80.77	24.31	97.83
C4.5 DT + BE	74.16	57.14	19.03	94.84
GBT + BE	69.05	47.80	39.03	80.09
XGBoost + BE	73.20	52.97	26.94	90.49

Table 3 illustrates the outcomes of the experiments that were conducted. Model 1 presents findings from research conducted using original data, wherein C4.5 DT exhibits an accuracy rate of 68.77%, a precision of 42.02%, a recall of 16.25%, and a specificity of 88.32%. In comparison, XGBoost follows with an accuracy of 67.83%, a precision of 39.39%, a recall of 21.94%, and a specificity of 84.86%. GBT trails behind with an accuracy of 63.77%, a precision of 38.83%, a recall of 48.19%, and a specificity of 69.75%. These results still need more satisfaction, as evidenced by the relatively low accuracy values across all learning algorithms. The inconsistent precision, recall, and specificity values also hint at class imbalance issues.

Meanwhile, XGBoost achieved the highest accuracy score with a figure of 87.57%, precision of 87.46%, recall of 88.42%, and specificity of 86.79% in Model 2. Additionally, C4.5 DT and GBT have not shown better results; the accuracy values obtained by both learning algorithms are only 69.51% and 69.95%, respectively. Nevertheless, C4.5 DT and GBT still demonstrate slight improvements, 0.74%, and 6.18%, respectively. This model becomes the most effective model compared to others, as it achieves class balance, as seen from the precision, recall, and specificity figures, which are consistent. This result is different from research conducted by Natarajan *et al.* [37], which shows that gradient boosting is the best model when improved with SMOTE, producing a model performance with an area under the curve (AUC) value of 0.952.

In Model 3, the C4.5 DT algorithm, integrated with forward selection, achieved the highest accuracy value at 78.27%, with precision at 82%, recall at 28.33%, and specificity at 96.96%. Then, XGBoost attained the next highest accuracy level, scoring 77.94%, with precision at 80.77%, recall at 24.31%, and specificity at 97.83%. Conversely, integrated with backward elimination, GBT yielded the poorest results in this model, recording accuracy of 69.05%, precision of 47.80%, recall of 39.03%, and specificity of 80.09%. Using feature selection through this wrapper method failed to deliver satisfactory performance. Moreover, employing this method tends to be more time-consuming than previously established models. Conversely, the anticipated output from operational feature selection is determining the importance of features on the independent variables in this research.

The results revealed that XGBoost, integrated with the resampling method utilizing Bootstrapping and SMOTE, yielded the highest performance, achieving an accuracy score of 87.57%. This figure shows a higher result than Hochman *et al.* [38] investigated XGBoost’s capability in predicting PPD incidence, devising a Q-based model, and acquiring an AUC value of 0.712 in a nationwide birth cohort. Correspondingly, Hochman *et al.* [38] also noted a tendency towards low positive predictive value (PPV). This trend arises from the dataset’s low incidence of PPD. In our research, employing the resampling method, specifically Bootstrapping and SMOTE, still led to higher accuracy values. While other research [14], [39]–[41] shows RF as the best algorithm in building prediction models, this research provides new insights

into the use of ensemble learning with XGBoost, which also provides satisfactory prediction model performance.

The challenge encountered in other models within this study is the presence of class imbalance. For instance, in Model 1 utilizing C4.5 DT, a relatively high accuracy rate of 68.77% was achieved, yet the precision and recall values were notably low at 42.02% and 16.25%, respectively. Accuracy is defined as the proportion of correct predictions, encompassing both true positives and negatives, relative to the total predictions made. Conversely, recall represents the percentage of actual positive cases correctly identified by the algorithm, indicating its effectiveness in classifying positive cases. Additionally, precision denotes the probability of accurately predicting positive class instances, calculated as the ratio of true positives to the sum of true positives and negatives [42], [43]. This performance indicates a failure to correctly predict instances of the minority class despite the relatively high accuracy rate attained. Such class imbalance may lead to classification errors, diminishing the algorithm’s accuracy. Consequently, for a more comprehensive evaluation of model performance, considering all elements of the confusion matrix is imperative.

Figure 2 illustrates the features employed in this study, depicting the relationship between independent and dependent variables utilized in the feature selection process through FS and BE. This figure shows that FS tends to yield fewer associated variables compared to BE. This discrepancy arises because FS initiates with each feature and subsequently iterates by gradually incorporating additional features, whereas, BE involves utilizing all features initially and then progressively eliminating them at each iteration. Ultimately, the figure underscores marital status, number of living children, history of depression, fear of delivery, and relationship with the family as pivotal factors in this research; each was selected five times in both feature selection methods.

	FS with C4.5 DT	FS with GBT	FS with XGBoost	BE with C4.5 DT	BE with GBT	BE with XGBoost	Size of Feature Subset
Maternal age							3
Ethnicity							2
Marital status							5
Highest education attainment							3
Occupation							3
Gross monthly income							3
Gravida							3
Parity							3
Mode of delivery							3
Complication during pregnancy							2
Desire to be pregnant							3
No. of living children							5
History of abortion							3
Menstrual problem							3
Duration of delivery							3
Gestational age							3
Gender of the baby							2
Birth weight							3
Condition of the baby							4
History of depression							5
Fear of delivery							5
Disposition during pregnancy							3
Knowledge of parenting							3
Weight gain							2
Religion							3
Tradition in family							2
Relationship with husband							2
Relationship with family							5
Family and husband support							3
Blood type							3
History of depression in family							3

Figure 2. Complete list of features selected by each ML method

Meanwhile, the features consistently selected in the feature selection method employed in this study include marital status, number of living children, history of depression, fear of delivery, and relationship with family. In a marital relationship, the status and quality of the relationship are essential. A high-quality relationship can offer the mother security, as there will be no suspicion within household dynamics. However, partners can also be sources of stress, depending on the relationship’s quality. Therefore, focusing on relationship quality rather than just status provides resources and enhances resilience [44]. Additionally, having more children can heighten the risk of postnatal depression. According to Antczak *et al.* [45], mothers with multiple children may experience family conflicts, particularly regarding childcare and education

responsibilities. Furthermore, a history of depression experienced by the mother before pregnancy and childbirth also contributes to the likelihood of PPD.

The prediction model developed in this study has yielded commendable outcomes, but certain limitations persist. The dataset comprises primary data, which remains relatively limited in quantity, suggesting the potential consideration of integrating electronic health records (EHR) for predicting PPD incidence. Although the prediction model showcased promising results, exploring alternative ensemble learning strategies, such as RF and adaptive boosting, could enhance model performance. This research holds significant value for healthcare professionals and the community, particularly postpartum mothers, as implementing ML-driven automatic PPD screening can streamline health assessment procedures, saving valuable time. Furthermore, prompt identification of PPD symptoms enables timely and appropriate interventions for affected mothers.

4. CONCLUSION

The combination of physical and emotional exhaustion after childbirth, coupled with hormonal fluctuations, can lead to mental health issues, notably PPD. Severe cases of PPD can escalate to postpartum psychosis, underscoring the critical need for swift and accurate screening methods facilitated by technological advancements. This research employs an ensemble learning model integrated with resampling and feature selection techniques to develop a model demonstrating optimal performance. The most effective prediction model for PPD is achieved through the XGBoost algorithm, integrated with Bootstrapping and SMOTE, yielding an accuracy rate of 87.57% and an AUC of 86.79%. Conversely, the GBT algorithm exhibits less robust performance across all models, with accuracy rates of 63.77% in Model 1, 69.95% in Model 2, 72.88% with forward selection, and 69.05% with backward elimination in Model 3. Furthermore, marital status, number of living children, history of depression, fear of delivery, and relationship with family emerge as independent variables correlated with the dependent variable. This study's PPD prediction model is potentially useful in clinical settings. Nevertheless, we assert that further development and optimization of this model are feasible through utilizing larger datasets and exploring alternative ensemble learning algorithms, as well as various resampling and feature selection methods.

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BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Winda Ayu Fazraningtyas received her bachelor's degree in Nursing Science from Lambung Mangkurat University, Banjarmasin, South Kalimantan, Indonesia. She has a strong interest in women's health, which led her to pursue a post-graduate program in the Master of Science in Nursing at St. Paul University Philippines. Currently, she is a Ph.D. student at the Graduate Program Faculty of Computing and Meta-Technology in Tanjung Malim, Perak, Malaysia. In addition to her academic pursuits, she serves as an Assistant Professor at the Department of Maternity Nursing, Faculty of Health, Sari Mulia University. She is also actively involved as a reviewer for indexed international journals. Her research interests i.e., women's mental health, maternity nursing focus on the postpartum period, violence against women, and machine learning. She can be contacted at email: windaayu@unism.ac.id.

Bahbibi Rahmatullah is currently an associate professor in the Department of Computing, Faculty of Computing and Meta-Technology, Sultan Idris Education University, Malaysia. Having received a B.Eng (Electrical) from Vanderbilt University, USA, a M.Eng.Sc from Multimedia University, Malaysia, and a D.Phil in Eng. Science from the University of Oxford, UK, she is keen to apply the technical and research skills gained to improve the quality of research and education in Malaysia. She has authored a wide range of publications and has been invited to review articles for high-impact journals and conferences. Current research interests include image and signal processing, pattern recognition, machine learning, learning analytics, child development, ICT, and education. She can be contacted at email: bahbibi@meta.upsi.edu.my.

Husni Naparin gained his undergraduate degree (S1) from the Department of Technical Information, Technical Faculty, Kalimantan Islamic University, Syekh Muhammad Arsyad Al-Banjary Banjarmasin in 2013 and Graduate Program (S2) from Faculty of Computer Science (Intelligence System), University of Dian Nuswantoro, Semarang, Jawa Tengah in 2015. He graduated Ph.D. program in the Faculty of Computing and Meta-Technology, Universitas Pendidikan Sultan Idris. His main research interest is information system, data mining, data visualization, and multimedia. He can be contacted at email: 1naparinhusni@gmail.com.

Mohammad Basit currently serves as a lecturer in the Nursing Department within the Faculty of Health at Sari Mulia University, located in Banjarmasin, South Kalimantan, Indonesia. His passion lies in utilizing his technical and research expertise to enhance the quality of research and education, particularly in Ward Nursing Management. He has contributed significantly to the field through numerous publications in nationally accredited and international journals and community service initiatives. Leveraging his extensive educational background, he also holds the position of Chair of the Nursing Department at Sari Mulia University. He can be contacted at email: syafabasit@gmail.com.

Nor Asiah Razak is currently a senior lecturer in the Software Engineering and Smart Technology Department at the Faculty of Computing and Meta-Technology, Sultan Idris Education University (UPSI). She earned her Ph.D. in Educational Technology from Universiti Putra Malaysia in 2019, focusing on e-learning. Her current research interests include digitalization in education, focusing on learning strategies for enhancing 21st-century learning skills. She also serves as a reviewer for national and international academic journals. She can be contacted at email: norasiah.razak@meta.upsi.edu.my.